

On the Edge Geodetic and k -Edge Geodetic Number of a Graph

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Abstract: For vertices u and v in a connected graph $G = (V, E)$, the distance $d(u, v)$ is the length of a shortest $u - v$ path in G . A $u - v$ path of length $d(u, v)$ is called a $u - v$ geodesic. For an integer $k \geq 1$, a geodesic of length k in G is called a k -geodesic. A set $S \subseteq V$ is a k -edge geodetic set of G if each edge $e \in E - E(< S >)$ lies on a k -geodesic of some pair of vertices in S and a set $T \subseteq V$ is an edge geodetic set of G if each edge of G lies on a geodesic of some pair of vertices in T , and Smarandache edge-geodetic set of G if each edge of G lies on at least two geodesics of T . The minimum cardinality of a k -edge geodetic set of G is the k -edge geodetic number $eg_k(G)$ and the minimum cardinality of an edge geodetic set is the edge geodetic number $eg(G)$. In this paper we investigate how the edge geodetic number and the k -edge geodetic number of a graph G are affected by adding a pendant edge to G . It is proved that if G' is a graph obtained from G by adding a pendant edge, then $eg(G) \leq eg(G') \leq eg(G) + 1$ and $eg_2(G) \leq eg_2(G') \leq eg_2(G) + 1$. For any integer $k \geq 2$, it is also proved that $eg_k(G') \leq eg_k(G) + 2$. It is shown that for any integer $k \geq 4$ and for every pair a, b of integers with $4 \leq a \leq b + 2$, there is a connected graph G such that $eg_k(G) = b$ and $eg_k(G') = a$, where G' is a graph obtained from G by adding a pendant edge.

Key Words: Smarandache edge-geodetic set, geodetic number, edge geodetic number, k -geodetic number, k -edge geodetic number, k -extreme edge.

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§1. Introduction

By a graph $G = (V, E)$, we mean a finite undirected connected graph without loops or multiple edges. The order and size of G are denoted by n and m respectively. For basic graph theoretic terminology, we refer to Harary [3]. For vertices u and v in a connected graph G , the distance $d(u, v)$ is the length of a shortest $u-v$ path in G . It is known that the distance is a metric on the vertex set of G . A $u-v$ path of length $d(u, v)$ is called a $u-v$ geodesic. A vertex x is said to lie on a $u-v$ geodesic P if x is a vertex of P including the vertices u and v . For any path P in a graph and two vertices x, y on P , we use $P[x, y]$ to denote the portion of P between x and y , inclusive of x and y . The neighborhood of a vertex v is the set $N(v)$ consisting of all vertices u which are adjacent with v . A vertex v is an extreme vertex of G if the subgraph induced by its neighbors is complete. The closed interval $I[u, v]$ consists of all vertices lying on

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some u - v geodesic of G , while for $S \subseteq V$, $I[S] = \bigcup_{u,v \in S} I[u,v]$. A set S of vertices is a *geodetic set* if $I[S] = V$, and the minimum cardinality of a geodetic set is the *geodetic number* $g(G)$. A geodetic set of cardinality $g(G)$ is called a *g -set* of G . The geodetic number of a graph was introduced in [1], [4] and further studied in [2], [5]. It was shown in [4] that determining the geodetic number of a graph is an NP-hard problem. A set S of vertices is an *edge geodetic set* of a graph G if each edge of G lies on a geodesic of vertices in S , and Smarandache edge-geodetic set of G if each edge of G lies on at least two geodesics of S . The minimum cardinality of an edge geodetic set is the *edge geodetic number* $eg(G)$. An edge geodetic set of cardinality $eg(G)$ is called *eg -set* of G . Edge geodetic sets and the edge geodetic number of a graph with several interesting applications are investigated in [7].

For an integer $k \geq 1$, a geodesic in G of length k is called *k -geodesic*. A vertex v is called *k -extreme vertex* if v is not the internal vertex of a k -geodesic joining any pair of distinct vertices of G . Obviously, each extreme vertex of a connected graph G is k -extreme vertex of G . In particular, each end vertex of G is a k -extreme vertex of G . A set $S \subseteq V$ is called a *k -geodetic set* of G if each vertex v in $V - S$ lies on a k -geodesic of vertices in S . The minimum cardinality of a k -geodetic set of G is its *k -geodetic number* $g_k(G)$. A k -geodetic set of cardinality $g_k(G)$ is called *g_k -set*. The k -geodetic number of a graph was referred to as *k -geodeomination number* and studied in [6].

For any $S \subseteq V$, let $E(< S >)$ denote the edge set of the subgraph induced by S . A set $S \subseteq V$ is called a *k -edge geodetic set* of G if each edge in $E - E(< S >)$ lies on a k -geodesic of vertices in S . The minimum cardinality of a k -edge geodetic set of G is its *k -edge geodetic number* $eg_k(G)$. A k -edge geodetic set of cardinality $eg_k(G)$ is called *eg_k -set* of G . For $k \geq 2$, an edge of G is called *k -extreme edge* if it does not lie on any k -geodesic of vertices of G .

For the graph G given in Fig.1.1, it is easy to see that the set $S = \{v_1, v_2, v_5, v_6\}$ of end vertices is a g_2 -set and so $g_2(G) = 4$. Since the edge v_3v_4 does not lie on any 2-geodesic of vertices of S , S is not a 2-edge geodetic set of G . It is easily seen that $S_1 = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6\}$ is a minimum 2-edge geodetic set of G so that $eg_2(G) = 5$. Also, $S_2 = \{v_1, v_2, v_4, v_5, v_6\}$ is another eg_2 -set of G .

Fig.1.1

The k -edge geodetic number of a graph was introduced and studied in [8]. It is proved in [8] that each triple a, b, k of integers with $2 \leq a \leq b$ and $k \geq 2$ is realizable as the k -geodetic number and k -edge geodetic number of a graph respectively. Also it is shown in [8] that for given integers a, b, c and $k \geq 2$ with $3 \leq a \leq b \leq c$, there is a connected graph G with

$g(G) = a$, $eg(G) = b$ and $eg_k(G) = c$. These concepts have many applications in location theory and convexity theory. There are interesting applications of these concepts to the problem of designing the route for a shuttle and communication network design.

A fundamental question in graph theory concerns how the value of a parameter is affected by making a small change in the graph. The geodetic number and the k -geodetic number, affected by adding a pendant edge, was discussed in [5] and [6] respectively. In this paper we study how the edge geodetic number and the k -edge geodetic number of a graph are affected by adding a pendant edge to the graph.

Throughout the following G denotes a connected graph with at least two vertices. The following theorems will be used in the sequel.

Theorem 1.1([7]) *Each extreme vertex of a connected graph G belongs to every edge geodetic set of G . In particular, if the set of all extreme vertices W is an edge geodetic set of G , then W is the unique eg-set of G .*

Theorem 1.2([8]) *Every k -edge geodetic set contains both the ends of each k -extreme edge. If the set W of the ends of all the k -extreme edges together with the set of k -extreme vertices is a k -edge geodetic set, then W is the unique eg_k -set of G and so $eg_k(G) = |W|$.*

Theorem 1.3([7]) *For any tree T with k end vertices, $eg(T) = k$.*

Theorem 1.4([7]) *For a connected graph G , $eg(G) = 2$ if and only if there exist two antipodal vertices u and v such that every edge lies on a $u - v$ geodesic of G .*

Theorem 1.5([7]) *For a connected graph G , no cut vertex belongs to any eg-set of G .*

Theorem 1.6([7]) *For the complete bipartite graph $K_{m,n}$ ($m, n \geq 2$), $eg(K_{m,n}) = \min\{m, n\}$.*

Theorem 1.7([7]) *If a connected graph G of order n has exactly one vertex v of degree $n - 1$ then $eg(G) = n - 1$.*

§2. How the edge geodetic number of a connected graph is affected by adding a pendant edge

In this section we discuss how the edge geodetic number of a connected graph G is affected by adding a pendant edge to G . Let G' be a graph obtained from a connected graph G by adding a pendant edge uv , where u is not vertex of G and v is a vertex of G .

Theorem 2.1 *If G' is a graph obtained from a connected graph G by adding a pendant edge uv at a vertex v of G , then $eg(G) \leq eg(G') \leq eg(G) + 1$.*

Proof Let S be any eg-set of G and let $S' = S \cup \{u\}$. We claim that S' is an edge geodetic set of G' . Let e be an edge of G' . If $e \in E(G)$, then e lies on a geodesic of vertices in S . If $e = uv$, then, since every edge geodetic set of G is a geodetic set of G , it follows that the vertex v lies on a $x - y$ geodesic P with $x, y \in S$. Then, it is clear that the portion $P[x, v]$ of the $x - v$ path on P together with the edge uv is a $x - u$ geodesic of G' , which contains the edge e with

$x, u \in S'$. Hence S' is an edge geodetic set of G' and so $eg(G') \leq eg(G) + 1$. Let S' be an eg -set of G' . By Theorems 1.1 and 1.5, $u \in S'$ and $v \notin S'$. Also, it is clear that $S = (S' - \{u\}) \cup \{v\}$ is an edge geodetic set of G so that $eg(G) \leq |S'| - 1 + 1 = |S'| = eg(G')$. Hence the result. \square

Remark 2.2 The bounds for $eg(G')$ in Theorem 2.1 are sharp. If the graph G is the path P_n ($n \geq 3$) on n vertices, then, by Theorem 1.3, $eg(P_n) = 2$. Let G' be the path obtained from P_n by adding a pendant edge at one of its end vertices. Then, by Theorem 1.3, $eg(G') = 2 = eg(G)$. If G' is the tree obtained from P_n by adding a pendant edge at a cut vertex of P_n , then by Theorem 1.3, $eg(G') = 3 = eg(G) + 1$.

Theorem 2.3 *Let G' be a graph obtained from a connected graph G by adding a pendant edge uv at a vertex v of G . Then $eg(G) = eg(G')$ if and only if v is a vertex of some eg -set of G .*

Proof First, assume that there is an eg -set S of G such that $v \in S$. Let $S' = (S - \{v\}) \cup \{u\}$. We show that S' is an eg -set of G' . If $e = uv$, then it is clear that e lies on every $w - u$ geodesic of G , where $w \in S'$ ($w \neq u$). Let e be any edge of G . Since S is an eg -set of G , e lies on a $x - y$ geodesic in G with $x, y \in S$. If both $x, y \in S - \{v\}$, then e also lies on a $x - y$ geodesic in G' with $x, y \in S'$. If e lies on a $x - v$ geodesic in G with $x \in S - \{v\}$, then e also lies on $x - u$ geodesic in G' . Thus S' is an edge geodetic set of G' so that $eg(G') \leq |S'| = |S| = eg(G)$. Now, the result follows from Theorem 2.1.

Conversely, suppose that $eg(G) = eg(G')$. Suppose that v does not belong to any eg -set of G . Let S' be an eg -set of G' . Since u is an end vertex of G' and v is a cut vertex of G' , by Theorems 1.1 and 1.5, $u \in S'$ and $v \notin S'$. Let $S = (S' - \{u\}) \cup \{v\}$. Then $S \subseteq V(G)$ and $|S| = |S'| = eg(G') = eg(G)$. Let e be any edge of G . Then e is also an edge of G' and so e lies on a geodesic P in G' joining a pair of vertices $x, y \in S'$. If $x \neq u$ and $y \neq u$, then $x \in S$ and $y \in S$ so that e lies on a geodesic joining a pair of vertices in S . Otherwise, let $x \neq u$ and $y = u$. Then it follows that e lies on a geodesic in G joining x and v in S . Thus, S is an edge geodetic set of G and since $|S| = eg(G)$, it follows that S is an eg -set of G . Since $v \in S$, this is contradiction to our assumption. This completes the proof. \square

Remark 2.4 If a vertex v is added to a connected graph G such that more than one edge is incident with v , then the edge geodetic number of the resulting graph can stay the same, increase significantly or decrease significantly. For example, for the complete bipartite graph $K_{m,n}$ we have, by Theorem 1.6, $eg(K_{m,n}) = m$ for all $2 \leq m \leq n$. However, if we add a new vertex to $K_{m,n}$ and join this vertex to all the vertices of the minimum partite set containing m vertices, the resulting graph is $K_{m,n+1}$ and again by Theorem 1.6, the edge geodetic number is m . Hence a new vertex may be added to a graph along with a large number of edges such that it does not affect the edge geodetic number. On the other hand, it is clear that $eg(C_n) = 2$ for all even $n \geq 4$. If we add a vertex v to this C_n and join v to all the vertices of C_n , the resulting graph is the wheel $K_1 + C_n$. Now, it follows from Theorem 1.7 that $eg(K_1 + C_n) = n$ and so the edge geodetic number of the resulting graph increases significantly. Also, it is clear that $eg(K_{1,n}) = n$ for all $n \geq 2$. If we add a vertex v and join it to all the end vertices of $K_{1,n}$ then we obtain the graph $K_{2,n}$. By Theorem 1.6, $eg(K_{2,n}) = 2$, and so the edge geodetic number of the resulting graph decreases significantly for large n .

§3. How the k -edge geodetic number of a connected graph is affected by adding a pendant edge

We now consider how the k -edge geodetic number of a connected graph G is affected by the addition of a pendant edge.

Proposition 3.1 *Let G' be a graph obtained from a connected graph G by adding a pendant edge uv at a vertex v of G . Then $eg_k(G') \leq eg_k(G) + 2$.*

Proof Let S be an eg_k -set of G . Then $S \cup \{u, v\}$ is a k -edge geodetic set of G' and so $eg_k(G') \leq |S \cup \{u, v\}| \leq eg_k(G) + 2$. \square

Proposition 3.2 *There is no connected graph G with $diam(G) \geq k$ such that $eg_k(G') = 2$, where G' is a graph obtained from G by adding a pendant edge at a vertex of G .*

Proof Suppose that there exists a connected graph G with $diam(G) \geq k$ such that $eg_k(G') = 2$. Let G' be a graph obtained from G by adding a pendant edge uv at a vertex v of G . By Theorem 1.1, u belongs to every edge geodetic set of G' . Let $S' = \{u, y\}$ be an eg_k -set of G' . Then $y \neq v$ and it is clear that $S = \{v, y\}$ is a eg_{k-1} -set of G . Hence S is an eg -set of G and $d(v, y) = k - 1$. Now, by Theorem 1.4, v and y are antipodal vertices and so $diam(G) = k - 1$, which is a contradiction. Hence the result follows. \square

Observation 3.3 In a connected graph G , each edge in G has at least one end in every 2-edge geodetic set of G .

Theorem 3.4 *If G' is a graph obtained from a connected graph G by adding a pendant edge at a vertex of G , then $eg_2(G) \leq eg_2(G') \leq eg_2(G) + 1$.*

Proof Let G' be the graph obtained from G by adding a pendant edge uv at a vertex v of G . Let S be an eg_2 -set of G . Let $S' = S \cup \{u\}$. We claim that S' is a 2-edge geodetic set of G' . Let e be an edge of G' be such that $e \notin E(\langle S' \rangle)$. If $e \in E(G)$, then e lies on a 2-geodesic of vertices in S . If $e \notin E(G)$, then $e = uv$ and $v \notin S$. Let vw be an edge of G . Then, by Observation 3.3, we have $w \in S$. Now, it is clear that the edge uv lies on the 2-geodesic $P : w, v, u$ of G' with $w, u \in S'$. Hence S' is a 2-edge geodetic set of G' and so $eg_2(G') \leq |S'| = eg_2(G) + 1$.

Now, let T' be any eg_2 -set of G' . Then by Theorem 1.2, $u \in T'$. Let $T = (T' - \{u\}) \cup \{v\}$. Then $|T| \leq |T'|$. We show that T is a 2-edge geodetic set of G . Let $e = xy$ be any edge of G such that $e \notin E(\langle T \rangle)$. Then it is clear that $e \notin E(\langle T' \rangle)$. Now, since $e \in E(G')$ and T' is a eg_2 -set of G' , we see that $e = xy$ lies on a 2-geodesic P of vertices in T' . By Observation 3.3, we may assume that $x \in T'$. Assume that the geodesic P is $P : x, y, z$ with $x, z \in T'$. Since $xy \in E(G)$, we have $x \neq u$ and so $x \in T$. Now, if $z = u$, then $y = v$ and so $xy \in E(\langle T \rangle)$, which is a contradiction. Hence $z \neq u$ and so $z \in T$. Thus T is a 2-edge geodetic set of G so that $eg_2(G) \leq |T| \leq |T'| = eg_2(G')$. \square

Proposition 3.5 *Let G' be a graph obtained from a connected graph G by adding a pendant*

edge uv at a vertex v of G . If v belongs to some eg_2 -set of G' , then $eg_2(G') = eg_2(G) + 1$.

Proof Let T' be an eg_2 -set of G' such that $v \in T'$. By Theorem 1.2, $u \in T'$. Now, let $T = T' - \{u\}$. Then $|T| = |T'| - 1 = eg_2(G') - 1$ and as in the proof of Theorem 3.4, T is a 2-edge geodetic set of G so that $eg_2(G) \leq |T| = eg_2(G') - 1$. Now, the result follows from Theorem 3.4. \square

Remark 3.6 The converse of Theorem ?? is not true. For the graph $G = K_{1,n}$ ($n \geq 2$), we have that $eg_2(G) = n$. However, if we add a pendant edge to the cut vertex of $K_{1,n}$, then the resulting graph G' is $K_{1,n+1}$ and so $eg_2(G') = n + 1 = eg_2(G) + 1$. However, the cut vertex of $K_{1,n+1}$ does not belong to any eg_2 -set of $K_{1,n+1}$.

Problem 3.7 Characterize graphs G for which $eg_2(G') = eg_2(G)$, where G' is a graph obtained from G by adding a pendant edge.

In view of Proposition 3.1, we have the following realization theorem.

Theorem 3.8 Let $k \geq 4$ be an integer. For each pair a, b of integers with $4 \leq a \leq b + 2$, there is a connected graph G with $eg_k(G) = b$ and $eg_k(G') = a$, where G' is a graph obtained from G by adding a pendant edge.

Proof We prove the theorem by considering five cases.

Case 1. Let $a = b$. Let G be the graph obtained from the path $P : v_0, v_1, \dots, v_k$ by adding $b - 3$ new vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{b-3} and joining them to v_2 . The graph G is shown in Fig.3.1. It is clear that the edges $u_i v_2$ ($1 \leq i \leq b - 3$) are the only k -extreme edges of G . Hence $S = \{v_0, v_k, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{b-3}, v_2\}$ is the set of all k -extreme vertices and the ends of all k -extreme edges of G . Since S is a k -edge geodetic set of G , it follows from Theorem 1.2 that $eg_k(G) = |S| = b$.

Now, let G' be the graph obtained from G by adding a pendant edge $v_k x$. It is clear that G' has no k -extreme edges. Let $S' = \{v_0, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{b-3}, x\}$ be the set of all k -extreme vertices of G' . Since the edges $v_0 v_1$ and $v_1 v_2$ do not lie on any k -geodesic joining a pair of vertices in S' , we have S' is not a k -edge geodetic set of G' . Since $S' \cup \{v_k\}$ is a k -edge geodetic set of G' , it follows from Theorem 1.2 that $eg_k(G') = |S'| + 1 = b = a$.

Fig.3.1

Case 2. $a = b + 1$. Let G be the graph obtained from the path $P : v_0, v_1, \dots, v_k$ by adding $b - 2$ new vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{b-2} and joining each u_i to v_1 . Let $S = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{b-2}, v_0, v_k\}$.

Then S is the set of all k -extreme vertices of G . It is clear that G has no k -extreme edges and S is a k -edge geodetic set of G and so by Theorem 1.2, $eg_k(G) = |S| = b$. Now, let G' be the graph obtained from G by adding a new vertex x and joining it to v_1 . Then, just as above, the set $S' = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{b-2}, x, v_0, v_k\}$ of all k -extreme vertices of G' is the eg_k -set of G' . Hence $eg_k(G') = |S'| = b + 1 = a$.

Case 3. $a = b + 2$. Let G be the graph constructed in Case 2. Then, as in Case 2, $eg_k(G) = b$. Now, let G' be the graph obtained from G by adding a new vertex x and joining it to v_2 . Then the edge xv_2 is the only k -extreme edge in G' . Since the set $S' = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{b-2}, v_0, v_k, x, v_2\}$ of all k -extreme vertices together with the ends of the k -extreme edge xv_2 is a k -edge geodetic set, it follows from Theorem 1.2 that $eg_k(G') = |S'| = b + 2 = a$.

Case 4. $a = b - 1$. Let G_1 be the graph obtained from the path $P : v_0, v_1, \dots, v_k$ by adding a new vertex w and joining it to the vertices v_1, v_2 and v_3 . Let $Q : x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{k-2}$ be a path such that it is vertex disjoint with G_1 . Let G_2 be the graph obtained from G_1 and Q by identifying the vertices v_2 and x_0 . Let G be the graph obtained from G_2 by adding $b - 5$ new vertices z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{b-5} and joining each z_i to v_1 . The graph is G shown in Fig.3.2. It is clear that the edge v_2w is the only k -extreme edge of G . Since the set $S = \{v_0, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{b-5}, v_k, x_{k-2}, v_2, w\}$ of all k -extreme vertices and the ends of the k -extreme edge v_2w of G is a k -edge geodetic set, it follows from Theorem 1.2 that $eg_k(G) = |S| = b$.

Fig.3.2

Now, let G' be the graph obtained from G by adding a pendant edge wx . It is clear that G' has no k -extreme edges. Since the set $S' = \{v_0, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{b-5}, x, v_k, x_{k-2}\}$ of all k -extreme vertices of G' is a k -edge geodetic set of G' , it follows from Theorem 1.2 that $eg_k(G') = |S'| = b - 1 = a$.

Case 5. $4 \leq a \leq b - 2$. Let G_1 be the graph obtained from the path $P : v_0, v_1, \dots, v_k$ by adding a new vertex w and joining it to both v_2 and v_4 . Let G_2 be the graph obtained from G_1 by adding $b - a - 1$ new vertices $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{b-a-1}$ and joining each u_i to the vertices v_2, v_3, v_4 and w . Let G_3 be the graph obtained from G_2 by adding $a - 4$ new vertices z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{a-4} and joining each z_i to v_1 . Let $Q : x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{k-3}$ be a path such that it is vertex disjoint with G_3 . Let G be the graph obtained from G_3 and Q by identifying the vertices v_3 and x_0 . The

graph G is shown in Fig.3.3. It is clear that the edges $u_i v_3$ and $u_i w$ ($1 \leq i \leq b - a - 1$) are the only k -extreme edges of G and so by Theorem 1.2, the vertices $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{b-a-1}, v_3, w$ belong to every k -edge geodetic set of G .

Fig.3.3

First, suppose that $k = 4$. Let $S = \{v_0, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{b-a-1}, v_3, w, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{a-4}, x_1\}$. Then S is the set of all k -extreme vertices and the ends of all k -extreme edges of G . It is clear that S is not a k -edge geodetic set of G and $S \cup \{v_4\}$ is a k -edge geodetic set of G so that by Theorem 1.2, $eg_k(G) = |S| + 1 = b - 1 + 1 = b$. Now, let G' be the graph obtained from G by adding a new vertex x and joining it to w . Then the graph G' has no k -extreme edges. Let $S' = \{v_0, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{a-4}, x, x_1\}$. Then S' is the set of all k -extreme vertices of G' . It is clear that S' is not a k -edge geodetic set of G' and $S' \cup \{v_4\}$ is a k -edge geodetic set of G' so that by Theorem 1.2, $eg_k(G') = |S'| + 1 = a - 1 + 1 = a$. Next, suppose that $k \geq 5$. Let $T = \{v_0, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{b-a-1}, v_3, w, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{a-4}, x_{k-3}, v_k\}$. Then T is the set of all k -extreme vertices and the ends of all k -extreme edges of G . It is clear that T is a k -edge geodetic set of G and so by Theorem 1.2, $eg_k(G) = |T| = b$.

Let G' be the graph obtained from G by adding a new vertex x and joining it to w . Then G' has no k -extreme edges and $T' = \{v_0, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{a-4}, x, x_{k-3}, v_k\}$ is the set of all k -extreme vertices of G' . Since T' is a k -edge geodetic set of G' , it follows from Theorem 1.2 that $eg_k(G') = |T'| = a$. Thus the proof is complete. \square

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